

Effects of Processing Methods on Nutritional, Functional and Sensory Attributes Of Complementary Food Made From Selected Cereals and Legumes in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

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Abstract

Various processing methods are used widely in preparation of complementary foods. These processing methods are known to have effect on the overall nutritional profiles of formulations. This study evaluated the effects of these methods, specifically, soaking and roasting on a local complementary food that is prepared by mixing cereals and legumes at 3:2 ratios respectively. The proximate, functional, antinutritional, mineral and Amino acid content, storage stability and microbial analysis were conducted on two samples F1 (Soaked) and F2 (Roasted) of the complementary food formulation using standard analytical techniques. The results showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$), in the proximate properties. F1 showed increased crude fat ($0.33 \pm 23.43\%$), protein ($0.22 \pm 10.93\%$), fiber ($0.46 \pm 15.73\%$) and energy density (457.99 k/cal) while F2 showed increased carbohydrate ($0.41 \pm 63.05\%$), moisture ($0.07 \pm 2.45\%$) and ash content ($0.19 \pm 2.92\%$). A significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed in the antinutritional content, with F2 having lower values compared to F1 for both oxalate ($0.02 \pm 0.46 \text{ meq/L}$) and phytate ($0.03 \pm 0.36 \text{ meq/L}$). However, no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) was observed in storage stability and sensory attributes although F2 had the highest overall acceptability score (29.5) for the sensory attributes. A significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed in bulk density, swelling index and mineral content. F1 sample recorded the highest level of sodium ($0.81 \pm 15.86 \text{ mg/dl}$), iron ($0.00 \pm 1.51 \text{ mg/dl}$), copper ($0.02 \pm 0.20 \text{ mg/dl}$), and potassium ($0.00 \pm 24.57 \text{ mg/dl}$) while F2 had higher amounts of phosphorus ($0.52 \pm 18.81 \text{ mg/dl}$), calcium ($0.23 \pm 69.54 \text{ mg/dl}$) and magnesium ($0.08 \pm 19.64 \text{ mg/dl}$). Higher Amino acid content was observed in F1 except in theanine, whose value was higher in F2. Low bacterial count was recorded for both samples and no toxic microbes were identified. Overall, the result showed that each processing method (soaking and roasting) had a varying effect on the complementary food formulations; this can be used to target and improve specific desirable properties when preparing complementary foods.

Keywords: Complementary foods, functional properties, nutritional content, processing methods, sensory attributes

1.0 Introduction

Complementary foods are any nutrient-containing foods or liquids other than breast milk given to infants during the period of complementary feeding (6–24 months) [1]. The growth of an infant in the first 2 years is very rapid and breast

feeding alone will not meet the infant's nutritional requirements. The ability of breast milk to meet the requirements for macronutrients and micronutrients becomes limited with the increasing age of infants. Thus, timely introduction of complementary foods during infancy is necessary for both nutritional and

developmental reasons. However, the capacity of a complementary diet to meet the protein-energy requirements of infants depends on its nutritional quality [2].

Malnutrition during this period of life may lead to permanent and total stunted growth which might have a serious effect on brain development and other functional effects in the body. Protein-energy malnutrition refers to diseases arising from coincident lack in varying proportions of proteins and/or calories, which occurs most frequently in infants and young children and is commonly associated with some infections such as kwashiorkor and marasmus. Protein-energy malnutrition is a major health problem, especially in developing countries and contributes to death rate of infants, low physical and intellectual development of infants as well as reduced resistance to diseases and consequently stifles development [5].

To reduce child malnutrition, it is essential to provide nutritious food, breastfeeding, hygiene, healthcare, and prenatal care. However, poverty and food insecurity make it difficult for families to access nutrient-rich diets. Diets primarily based on plant sources with limited animal products or fortified foods often fall short of providing adequate protein, vitamins, minerals, and essential fatty acids. To address this, improvements such as processing (e.g., dehulling, fermenting), fortification, and adding animal-source foods like milk are needed. Specially formulated foods like fortified blended foods, commercial infant cereals, or ready-to-use foods (RUFs) can help, as well as complementary food supplements containing micronutrients, protein, and fats. While many feeding programs use fortified blended foods, these may have limitations, including high antinutrient content, lack of milk, and suboptimal nutrient content [6].

The recommended characteristics of complementary food are summarized according to [3]. The meals should be rich in calories, good quality protein, vitamins, and minerals. When the food is stirred with cold or warm water or milk, the food should form a slurry or semi-solid mass of soft consistency to enable easy swallowing by the child. The prepared meal should be low in dietary bulk. The food should be processed in such

a way that it requires minimum preparation prior to feeding and is easily digested. The food should be free from anti-nutritional factors and low in non digestible fibre content [4].

The processing method of some complementary food has shown to have some significant effects on the viscosity, dietary bulkiness and its nutrient density. The major food ingredient in cereal based complementary foods is the starch component. It is also regarded to be the major water-binding component in most complementary foods and to a large extent; it determines the dietary bulk properties according to [5]. The processing of complementary food could be in the form of milling (dry and wet milling), thermal processing, germination, fermentation, roasting/cooking, soaking, autoclaving/sterilization and enzyme treatment.

Complementary foods, particularly those derived from cereals and legumes, play a vital role in meeting the nutritional needs of the vulnerable population. However, the nutritional quality, functional properties, and sensory acceptability of these foods can be significantly influenced by the various processing methods employed during their production. Understanding the impact of these processing techniques is crucial for several reasons. First, it allows for the development of complementary foods that are not only nutritionally balanced but also palatable, thereby increasing the likelihood of their acceptance and consumption by infants and young children [7]. Second, optimizing these processing methods can lead to cost reductions, making these essential foods more accessible to low-income populations [8]. Lastly, improvements in flavor and shelf life can enhance the overall quality and marketability of these products.

A common complementary food used in the northern region of Nigeria is 'sabaya,' made from selected cereals and legumes blended together into a powder given to infants as porridge. The incorporation of legumes in this complementary food enhances its protein content [9]. Given the importance of complementary foods in infant nutrition and the potential impact of processing methods on their quality and nutrient availability, there is a need to assess the effects of these processing methods on the nutritional, functional,

and sensory attributes of complementary foods. Consequently, this research aims to determine the effects of processing methods on the nutritional, functional, and sensory attributes of complementary foods.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials procurement

Wheat, white rice, soybeans, groundnut and sesame were obtained from Birninkebbi Central Market, Kebbi State, Nigeria as at July, 2024. The cereals and legumes were authenticated by a qualified botanist at the department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Birninkebbi, Samples of the authenticated materials with voucher numbers, FUBK-H_222 for *Triticum aestivum* L., *Oryza sativa* L. (FUBK-H_221), *Glycine max* L. (FUBK-H_220), *Arachis hypogaea* L. (FUBK-H_219) *Sesamum indicum* L. (FUBK-H_223) respectively, were deposited in the herbarium section of the department.

2.2 Preparation of Complementary Food Samples [Soaked sample - F1 & Roasted sample - F2]

The ingredients for both samples were optimized using the Nutri-Survey Linear Programming application for nutritional balance, with a composition of 30g white rice, 30g wheat, 20g groundnut, 10g sesame, and 10g soybeans per 100g of sample, mixed in a 3:2 ratio for cereals and legumes, respectively. For Soaked sample (F1), the ingredients were sorted, washed, soaked separately for 6-8 hours, drained, and dried overnight at room temperature before being mixed, milled into powder, and stored. For Roasted sample (F2), the ingredients were sorted, washed, and dried overnight at room temperature, then roasted individually for 20 minutes on medium heat until a color change and aroma were observed, followed by mixing, milling into fine powder, and storage for evaluation.

2.3 Proximate Analysis

Proximate composition was determined in triplicate using standard procedures of Association of Official Analytical Chemists [10].

2.4 Determination of Functional Properties.

2.4.1 pH Measurement

The pH was measured by making a 10% (w/v) suspension of each sample in distilled water. Each sample was mixed thoroughly in a beaker, and the pH was recorded with an electronic pH meter (Model PHN-850, Villeurbanne, France) [12].

2.4.2 Bulk Density (BD)

Twenty grams (20g) of sample was poured into a 100cm³ graduated cylinder. The cylinder was tapped 40 to 50 times and the bulk density was calculated as weight per unit volume of sample using equation 1.

$$BD = \frac{\text{Weight of sample (g)}}{\text{volume of sample (cm}^3\text{)}} \quad (1)$$

2.4.3 Swelling Index (SI)

Four grams (4g) of each of the samples was poured into a 50cm³ measuring cylinders and leveled gently. 40cm³ of distilled water was added to each sample and the cylinders swirled. After allowing the solutions to stand for 1hour, the volume was measured. The difference between the final and initial volume gives the swelling index. The SI was calculated using equation 2.

$$SI = \frac{\text{change in volume of sample}}{\text{original weight of sample}} \quad (2)$$

2.4.4 Water Absorption Capacity (WAC)

The weight of the clean centrifuge tubes were weighed, 2g of dried grinded sample was dispersed into centrifuge tube which dispensed 20cm³ of distilled water onto it and stirred with glass rod for 1minute. The tubes were centrifuged at 5000rpm for 30minutes. The volume of the supernatant was decanted and the tube with its content was reweighed as water absorbed per gram of sample. Equation 3 was used for the estimation.

$$WAC = \frac{\text{density of water} \times \text{volume absorbed}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

2.4.5 Reconstitution Index (RI)

From the ground sample, five grams of each sample was dissolved in 50cm³ of boiling water. The mixture was agitated for 90 seconds and was

transferred into a 50cm³ graduated cylinder and the volume of the sediment was recorded after settling for 30 minutes [13]. The RI was calculated using equation 4.

$$RI = \frac{\text{Volume of sediment}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \text{-----} (4)$$

2.5 Determination of Selected Mineral Elements.

Iron, Magnesium, Copper, Phosphorus, Sodium, Potassium and Calcium content was determined by means of atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Shimadzu AA-6200 Tokyo, Japan) according to AOAC method [11].

2.6 Peroxide Value Determination

Two grams (2g) of the flour sample was weighed into a clean dry flask and 22 cm³ of the mixture of 10 cm³ of acetic acid and 12 cm³ of chloroform was added, then 0.5 cm³ of potassium iodide was also added. The flask was closed and allowed to stay with constant shaking for 1 minute. 30 cm³ of distilled water was then added and titrated against 0.1 M of sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) solution until an initial yellow colour disappeared and a faint blue colour appeared. The titration continued after the addition of 0.5 cm³ of starch indicator until there was a sudden disappearance of the blue colour, which signifies the end point. The peroxide value is often reported as the mL of 20 mM Na₂S₂O₃ per gram of sample [14]. Thus, peroxide value was calculated using equation 5.

$$\text{Peroxide value} = \frac{(S-B) \times M \times 100}{W} \text{-----} (5)$$

Where: peroxide value= mEq of peroxide per 100 g of sample, S=sample titre value (cm³), B=blank titre value (cm³), M= molarity of Na₂S₂O₃ (mEq/cm³), W=weight of flour

2.7 Free Fatty Acids

Two grams (2g) of the flour was transferred into a 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flask followed by the addition of 100 cm³ of ethanol and 2 cm³ of phenolphthalein indicator. After mixing the content properly, it was titrated against 0.04 M NaOH. The shaking continued until a slight pink color was observed, which was steady for about 30 seconds and signified the end point [14]. The % of free fatty acids was calculated using equation 6.

$$\%FFA = \frac{V \times M \times 28.2}{W} \text{-----} (6)$$

Where: % FFA = percentage of free fatty acids, V= average volume of NaOH used (cm³), M = molarity of NaOH, W = weight of the flour sample

2.8 Determination of Anti nutritional factors (Phytate and Oxalate)

2.8.1 Phytate

Phytic acid was extracted from 3g of sample with 3% trichloroacetic acid by shaking at room temperature followed by high speed centrifugation. Then the phytic acid was estimated by multiplying the amount of phytate-phosphorus by the factor 3.55.

2.8.2 Oxalate

One gram (1g) of sample was weighed into 100cm³ conical flask. Then, 75cm³ of 3 mol/l of H₂SO₄ was added. The solution was stirred intermittently for 1hour on magnetic stirrer and then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. 25cm³ of the sample filtrate was collected and titrated against hot (80-90°C) 0.1 N KMnO₄ to point where a faint pink color appeared that persisted for 30 seconds [11]. Oxalate was calculated using 1cm³ 0.1 permanganate = 0.006303g oxalate.

2.9 Sensory Evaluation

Organoleptic assessment was carried out on the complementary foods by semi-trained panelists. The panelist were served with the same quantity of the samples simultaneously in clean disposable cups and clean water was provide for the panelist to rinse their mouth in-between evaluations. The samples was evaluated for color, flavor, taste, texture and over all acceptability on a 9-point Hedonic scale where 1 and 9 represent dislike extremely and like extremely respectively.

2.10 Determination of Amino Acid Profile of the Formulations

Amino acid determination was carried out using amino acid analyzer, TSM (Technicon Instruments Corporation, Dublin, Ireland). Two gram (2g) of the sample was defatted with petroleum ether using soxhlet extractor. The defatted sample was

re-dried and milled into fine powder using porcelain pestle and mortar. 30mg sample was weighed into glass ampoules to which 5cm³ of 6 M HCl and 5µmoles norleucine were added. The ampoule was evacuated by passing nitrogen gas (to remove oxygen so as to avoid possible oxidation of some amino acids during hydrolysis), sealed with Bunsen burner flame and hydrolyzed in an oven at 1100c for 24 hours.

The ampoules were cooled, broken at the tip and the content filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness at 400c under vacuum in a rotary evaporator. The residues were dissolved to 5µL (for acid and neutral amino acids) or 10µL (for basic amino acid) with acetate buffer, pH 2.2 and the solutions were dispensed into the centrifuge of TMS. The chromatograms (amino acid peaks) obtained from automatic pen recorder correspond to the quantity of each amino acid present. Quantification was performed by comparing the peak area of each amino acid in the sample to the area of the corresponding amino acid standard of the protein hydrolysate.

2.11 Determination of β-carotene

The β-carotene content was determined using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer by measuring the absorbance of the extract and the blank solution at 450 nm. Using the Beers Lambert law from measured absorbance data, its concentration was calculated in mg·l⁻¹

2.12 Determination of iodine value

To 5cm³ of chloroform solution of the fat sample, 5cm³ of Dam's reagent was added. The mixture was kept in fume cupboard for 10 min. and 5cm³ of 10% KI and 20cm³ of water were added. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and titrated to a colourless end point with 0.025M Na₂S₂O₃ solution.

2.13 Microbial analysis

2.13.1 Sample preparation and serial dilution

Ten grams (10g) of the samples were weighed and dissolved in 90mls of sterile water. The samples were mashed separately with pestle inside a mortar to obtain homogeneity. 1ml of the stock solution of the sample was transferred into 9mls of sterile water in plastic screwed capped test tubes and

shaken. 1ml from the first test tube was drawn and dispensed into the second test tube containing 9ml of sterile water, this process of serial dilution continued till the last test tube.

2.13.2 Media Used

Different media were used for different analytical purpose in this study. The Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was used for the isolation of fungi from the sample. Czapek Dox Agar (CDA) was used for sub-culturing. Nutrient Agar (NA) was used for isolation of bacteria from the sample, while MacConkey Agar (MA) was used for sub-culturing of bacteria. Biochemical media were used to characterize the organism into species on the basis of chemical reaction.

2.13.3 Inoculation of samples

Form the samples 10-2 and 10-4 serially diluted test tube, 1ml was withdrawn and dispensed into sterile petridishes. Molten agar was poured and swirled gently to mix. It was allowed to solidify and incubated at 37°c inside incubator for 18-24 hrs to observe the bacterial colony growth.

2.13.4 Counting of Bacteria

The microbes of colony forming units (CFU) were counted by dividing each of the petri dishes into four quadrant, then the number of colonies in one quadrant were counted and multiplied by four.

2.13.5 Subculture

The mixed bacterial colonies from the primary cultured plates were purified by transferring distinct colony to freshly prepared nutrient agar plates by stricken. The plates were incubated at 37° for 18-24hrs to obtain a pure culture.

2.13.6 Gram staining

Bacteria smears were made from pure cultured plate by dropping a drop of distilled water on the glass slide. Sterile wire loop was used to pick a colony and mixed with the drop of water, it was then speared to obtain a thin smear and allowed to air dry and heat fixed over the flame. The smeared glass slides were covered with crystal violet stain for 60seconds, the slides were rinsed with clean water, and the smear was flooded with Lugol's iodine for 60seconds. They were washed with

clean water and decolorized with 95% ethanol for 10-15seconds. The smears were counter stained using safarin for 30 seconds. They were washed and allowed to air dry before mounting on the microscope.

2.13.7 Biochemical Tests

The biochemical tests carried out include the catalase test (bubbles indicating a positive result), oxidase test (purple color), citrate test (royal blue color), motility test (growth diffusion), indole test (red ring), glucose/lactose fermentation test (sugar fermentation and gas production), and urease test (pink color).

2.13.8 Identification of Fungal Isolates

The fungal isolates were identified using Czapek Dox Agar (CDA) for macroscopic identification, while the microscopic features were identified using slide culture techniques.

For slide culture using sterile petridish, a sterile filter paper was placed in a sterile U-shaped glass rod which was placed on a sterile filter paper. Afterward, about 4ml of sterile water was poured on sterile filter paper to completely moisten it, using forceps a sterile slide was placed on the upper end of U-shaped rod. Gently, a knife was flamed and used to cut a 5mm square block of the medium from the plate of Potatoes Dextrose Agar medium and the medium was picked up by inserting knife and carefully transferred this block aseptically to the centre of the slide. Inoculation was done in four sides of the medium with spores or mycelia fragments of the fungus to be examined, and a loop prior to spores was flamed. Aseptically a sterile cover glass was placed on the upper surface of the agar cube, and was pressed down slightly with the tip of the finger to expel

any air bubble and further disintegrate the hyphal growth to enhance observation. Petri dish cover was placed and incubated at room temperature for 7 days. The slides were observed under X40 of a compound microscope every day. Microscopic characteristics of fungi such as hyphae, conidial heads and arrangements of conidia were observed.

2.14 Statistical Analysis

Data were reported as means standard error of mean of triplicate determination. T-test was used to establish significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Values were analyzed using the SPSS statistical package.

3.0 Results

3.1 Proximate Composition of the Complementary Food Formulations

The proximate composition of F1 and F2 sample are presented in (Table 1). A significant ($P < 0.05$) differences was observed only in fat and carbohydrate content of F1 and F2 with p values 0.076 and 0.021 respectively. However, there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference in moisture, ash, fiber, and protein, contents for F1 and F2. The fat content of F1 is significantly higher than that of F2 although both meet the recommended amounts according to FAO (2011) [15].

3.2 Functional Properties of the Complementary Food Formulations

The functional properties of F1 and F2 sample were presented in (Table 2). A significant ($P < 0.05$) differences was observed only in bulk density and swelling index of F1 and F2 with p values 0.016 and 0.016 respectively. While there were no significant ($P > 0.05$) differences in water absorption and reconstitution index in F1 and F2.

Table 1: Proximate Composition of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2].

Proximate composition	Soaked sample [F1]	Roasted sample [F2]	P value
Ash content (%)	2.08±0.10	2.92±0.19	0.393
Moisture content (%)	2.04±0.03	2.45±0.07	0.138
Fat content (%)	23.43±0.33	15.77±0.35	0.076*
Crude fiber content (%)	15.73±0.46	9.58±0.16	0.362
Crude protein content (%)	10.93±0.22	6.07±0.09	0.175
Carbohydrate content (%)	50.85±4.87	63.05±0.41	0.021*
Energy density(k/cal)	457.99	418.41	

Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation. Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different P value < 0.05

Table 2: Functional properties of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Parameters	soaked sample F1	roasted sample F2	P value
Bulk Density (g/cm³)	0.86±0.00	0.87±0.01	0.016*
Swelling Index (cm³/g)	0.00±0.00	0.17±0.06	0.016*
Water Absorption (%)	0.28±0.04	0.55±0.01	0.132
Reconstitution Index	2.17±0.06	2.37±0.006	1.00

Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different (P<0.5) Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

3.3 Mineral Analysis of the Complementary Food Formulations

The mineral compositions of F1 and F2 are presented in (Table 3). A significant difference (p<0.05) was observed in iron, potassium and magnesium content of F1 and F2 with p values 0.016, 0.016 and 0.016 respectively. However, no significant difference (P>0.05) was observed in the levels of calcium, phosphorus, sodium and copper contents of F1 and F2.

3.4 Storage Stability of the Complementary Food Formulations

The percentage of free fatty acids and peroxide value, which are key indicators of storage stability are presented in the (Table 4) above. No significant difference (p>0.05) was observed in samples F1 and F2 over the course of four weeks.

Table 3: Mineral Analysis of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Sample	F1	F2	P value
Calcium (mg\dl)	65.33±0.29	69.54±0.23	0.534
phosphorus (mg\dl)	15.64±0.80	18.81±0.52	0.749
Sodium (mg\dl)	15.86±0.81	10.68±0.64	0.552
Iron (mg\dl)	1.51±0.00	1.35±0.00	0.016*
Potassium (mg\dl)	24.57±0.00	23.61±0.18	0.016*
Magnesium(mg\dl)	8.83±0.00	19.64±0.08	0.016*
Copper(mg\dl)	0.20±0.02	0.18±0.03	0.242

Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different (P<0.5) Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

Table 4: Storage Stability of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Parameters	WEEK 1		P value	WEEK2		P value
	F1	F2		F1	F2	
FFA(meq/L)	0.85±0.01	0.63±0.01	1.00	0.82±0.01	0.62±0.01	0.561
PV(meq/L)	0.67±0.00	0.44±0.00	0.561	0.67±0.00	0.44±0.01	0.137

Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different (P<0.5) Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

3.5 Anti nutritional properties of the Complementary Food Formulations

The results for phytate and oxalate contents of F1 and F2 are presented in (Table 5). A significant difference (p<0.05) is observed in both F1 and F2 with p values of 0.039 and 0.021 respectively.

3.6 Sensory attributes of soaked the Complementary Food Formulations

The sensory evaluation results from (Table 6) suggest that there is no significant difference (p>0.05) between F1 and F2 in terms of aroma, taste, color, and texture. This implies that both F1 and F2 are comparable in terms of sensory attributes. This shows that all the formulated

samples were well acceptable to the panelist. However, F2 roasted sample had the highest

overall acceptability score of (29.50) for the evaluation.

Table 5: Anti nutritional properties of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2].

Parameters	F1	F2	P value
Oxalate (%)	2.93±0.25	0.46±0.02	0.021*
Phytate(%)	4.91±0.13	0.36±0.03	0.039*

Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation
Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different (P<0.5)

Table 6: Sensory attributes of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Parameters	F1	F2	P value
Aroma	5.60±1.20	8.00±1.00	0.811
Taste	6.40±0.80	7.50±1.25	0.557
Color	7.9±0.47	6.50±2.65	0.188
Texture	6.8±1.78	7.50±1.45	0.788
Overall Acceptability	26.7	29.5	

Values are presented as mean ± SEM, values denoted with * are significantly different (P<0.5) Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

3.7 Essential Amino acid Content of the Complementary Food Formulations

The essential amino acid content of the complementary food formulations (F1: soaked and F2: roasted) is presented in Table 7. Phenylalanine content was higher in F1 compared to F2, suggesting that soaking retained more of this amino acid than roasting. Valine showed a slight decrease in F2 compared to F1, indicating minimal impact from roasting. Tryptophan, histidine, leucine, lysine, and isoleucine followed a similar trend, with higher levels in F1 than F2, suggesting a more significant loss of these amino acids during roasting. Interestingly, threonine showed higher levels in F2 (3.83 g/100 g) than F1 (3.10 g/100 g), suggesting roasting may enhance or retain this amino acid better than soaking. The variations observed in amino acid content reflect the differential impact of processing methods on amino acid stability and retention.

Table 7: Essential Amino acid Content of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Amino acid (g/100g)	F1	F2
Phenylalanine	4.08±0.01	3.28±0.57
Valine	3.97±0.06	3.68±0.01
Tryptophan	0.99±0.07	0.94±0.01
Histidine	3.02±0.58	2.24±0.14
Arginine	4.99±0.02	4.82±0.01
Leucine	10.62±0.05	6.30±0.01
Lysine	3.42±0.20	3.13±0.10
Threonine	3.10±0.10	3.83±0.03
Isoleucine	3.60±0.57	3.27±0.03
Methionine	1.42±0.01	1.28±0.01

Values are mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of triplicate determinations. The essential amino acid index (EAAI) can be used to categorize the quality of proteins as follows: EAAI≥0.95: indicate high quality; 0.86-0.95: good quality; 0.75-0.86: useful; ≤0.75: inadequate [36].Key:F1=Soaked complementary food formulation.and F2=Roasted complementary food formulation

3.9 β-carotene content of the Complementary Food Formulations

The β-carotene content of the complementary food formulations (F1: soaked and F2: roasted) is shown in Table 8. The β-carotene content was higher in F1 (974.0 µg/100 g) compared to F2 (924.0 µg/100 g). The superscripts indicate that the difference between the two values is statistically

significant ($P < 0.05$), highlighting that the processing method significantly affects the retention of β -carotene. Soaking appears to be more effective in preserving β -carotene content compared to roasting. The higher β -carotene level in F1 can be attributed to the milder conditions of soaking, which likely minimize oxidative and thermal degradation of β -carotene.

Table 8: β -carotene content of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Food samples	β -carotene ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$)
F1	974.0 ^f ±2.31
F2	924.0 ^e ±0.57

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM) of triplicate determinations. Values with different superscripts are significantly different at ($P < 0.05$). Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

3.10 Iodine Values of soaked the Complementary Food Formulations.

The iodine values of the complementary food formulations (F1: soaked and F2: roasted) are presented in Table 9. The iodine value for F1 (56.79) was significantly higher than that of F2 (27.33), with statistical analysis confirming that the difference is significant ($P < 0.05$). This result indicates that the processing method has a substantial impact on the retention of iodine in the food formulations. The higher iodine value in F1 suggests that soaking is more effective in preserving iodine content compared to roasting.

Table 9: Iodine Values of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Food Samples	Iodine Value(g/100g)
F1	56.79±0.05
F2	27.33 ±0.19

Table 11: Characterization of Gram positive Bacteria isolated from soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Sample	G/R	URE	MOT	IND	CIT	CAT	OXID	Isolate
F1	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Corynebacterium lcerans</i>
	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Corynebacterium equi</i>
F2	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Corynebacterium ovis</i>
	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Corynebacterium ulcerans</i>

Key: - =Negative, += Positive, GR= Gram reaction, URE – Urease test, MOT-Motility test, IND-Indole test, CIT- Citrate, CAT – Catalase test, OXID – Oxidase test. F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM) of triplicate determinations. Values with different superscripts are significantly different at ($P < 0.05$). Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

3.11 Microbial Load of the Complementary Food Formulations

The microbial analysis of the complementary food formulations was conducted to assess their safety and wholesomeness, with results summarized in Tables 10–13. The samples produced were analyzed for microbial load, primarily to determine their safety and wholesomeness. The bacteria and fungi loads of the complementary foods are within acceptable limits (Table 10). It reveals that the bacteria count was higher in F1 (32×10^{-3} cfu/g) than in F2 (26×10^{-3} cfu/g), while the fungi count was slightly higher in F2 (3×10^{-3} cfu/g) than in F1 (2×10^{-3} cfu/g). These counts are within acceptable safety limits, confirming that the samples are microbiologically safe for consumption.

The present study also attempted to isolate and characterize the bacteria associated with processing and storage (Table 11 & 12). All isolates were positive to urease and catalase test. Mycoflora isolated include *Aspergillus spp*, *Trichoderma spp* and *Neosartorya fischeri* (Table 13).

Table 10: Microbial count of soaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Samples	Bacteria (cfu/g)	Fungi (cfu/g)
F1	32±0.29 ^b ×10 ⁻³	2±0.26 ^a ×10 ⁻³
F2	26±0.56 ^a ×10 ⁻³	3±0.29 ^a ×10 ⁻³

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM) of triplicate determinations. Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

Table12: Characterization of Gram negative Bacteria Isolate fromsoaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2]

Sample	GR	URE	MOT	IND	CIT	CAT	OXID	Isolate
F1	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Kliebselia ozanae</i>
F2	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Kliebselia oedwardii</i>

Key: ND= Not detected, - =Negative, += Positive, GR= Gram reaction, URE – Urease test, MOT-Motility test, IND-Indole test, CIT- Citrate, CAT – Catalase test, OXID – Oxidase test. F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation

Table 13: Mycoflora Isolated fromsoaked sample [F1] and roasted sample [F2].

Mycoflora	F1	F2
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	-
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	-	+
<i>Trichoderma spp</i>	-	+
<i>Aspergillus phoenicis</i>	-	-
<i>Neosartorya fischeri</i>	-	-

Key: F1= Soaked complementary food formulation. and F2= Roasted complementary food formulation
+=Detected, -=Not detected.

4.0 Discussion

The processing method of some complementary food has shown to have some significant effects on the viscosity, dietary bulkiness and its nutrient density. The present study attempts to determine the effect of some selected processing methods (roasting and soaking) on the nutritional composition of a local complementary food formulated from selected cereals and legumes. The results obtained reveal a significant difference in the proximate composition of both samples. The fat content of F1 is significantly higher than that of F2 although both meet the recommended amounts according to [16]. Fat is important in the diet of infant and young children because it provide essential fatty acids, facilitates absorption of fat soluble vitamin, enhance dietary energy density and sensory quality. It has been recommended that during the complementary feeding period (6-12months), a child diet should derive 30-40% of energy from fat [17].

The carbohydrate content also differs, with F1 having a lower percentage than F2. The values recorded are similar to what was reported by Yusuf et al. [17]. When formulating food for infants, the ratio of fat, protein and carbohydrate must be taken into consideration as high protein to low carbohydrate ratio in the formulation will mean that the amino acids of the protein will be diverted to

glucose synthesis and the body will be deprived of protein meant for body building which will have a negative effect [17]. Both carbohydrate content of F1 and F2 meet the recommended limits by CAC (2017) [18]. The values recorded for energy density are higher than what was reported by Muhammed et al [19] and Akinsola et al. [20]. However, the higher energy density recorded agrees with what was reported by Tufa et al. [21] that high energy values can be linked to the addition of soybeans as his report also showed that the energy value of food samples was highest (442.46 and 430.57kcal/100g) in diets with soybean seeds.

The crude fiber content of the complementary foods in the present study was similar to values reported by Adeoye et al. [22]. He recorded similar values to those of F1 formulation which appeared to be higher than F2 formulation. The low fiber content is in accordance with the report that complementary food should contain low fiber as high fiber can lead to high water absorption and displacement of nutrient and important energy required for growth of children less than 24 months [17]. However, the good amount of fiber contents recorded are said to favorably modulate gut micro biota and maybe protect against diarrhea in sub Saharan Africa where rates in infants and young children are high [23]. The moisture sample for both F1 and F2 are significantly lower than values reported by Adeoye et al. [24] and Akinsola et al. [20]. The low moisture content is said to be indicative of a good shelf life and storage stability. The moisture contents of samples were within the acceptable limit of not more than 10% for long term storage of flour.

The protein content of F1 seems significantly higher than F2 but slightly lower than what was reported by Adeoye et al. [24]. Muhammed et al. [19] also noticed a drop in the levels of protein after roasting which he attributed to the occurrence of maillard reaction that happens in the presence of reducing sugars. The protein values are similar to what was reported by Anaemene et al. [25] for his soy based

samples. The calculations of the dietary requirement for whole protein suggest that a minimum protein energy ratio of 6% in complementary foods is desirable [31]. The ash content values reported for both samples are higher than those reported by Adeoye et al. [24] and Akinsola et al. [21]. The ash content of the formulation represents the mineral constituents of the foods which play vital roles in biochemical processes in the body; these processes are vital for efficient functioning and balance of the body.

Overall the values of proximate composition obtained, it is clear that processing has effect on the quality of the formulations. Soaking improved the overall nutritional profile of the formulation. This is in agreement with the work of Uffiah, 2024 [26] who recorded a general increase of moisture and carbohydrate content of sample after soaking. Agnes et al, [27] noted that soaking is not a good method for improving bioavailability of minerals which is consistent with the result obtained as F1 has lower ash content than F2. Roasting has marked effect mostly on the mineral, functional and sensory attributes of the formulation. Roasted F1 formulation had higher ash content, moisture and carbohydrate contents. It also had a higher score in terms of organoleptic properties and overall acceptance by panelists. This is consistent with the result reported by Agnes et al. [27] and Muhammad et al. [19].

Functionality of a food is the property of a food ingredient, apart from its nutritional value, that has a great impact on its utilization. During processing of most complementary foods emphasis is usually on the nutritional quality and quantity of the ingredients rather than their functional properties. The functional properties of the complementary food blends are presented in Table 4. Low swelling index is recorded for both samples. This shows that the formulations will be nutrient dense as they won't absorb a lot of water which will give them a thick and desirable consistency. High swelling index may reduce the nutrient density of the food and high water absorption is also disadvantageous as it limits the absorption of nutrients by the infant Adeoye et al. [24].

The values of bulk density are also low (< 1) which shows that the powder of the formulations will have high yield for prepared formulations. Bulk density is a measure of heaviness of flour sample and this

gives an indication that the relative volume of the composite flour in a package will not reduce excessively during storage. The WAC of a food product reflects its ability to absorb moisture. It is defined as the amount of moisture taken up by the flour to achieve a desired consistency or optimal result. The recorded values for water absorption capacity of both F1 and F2 are much lower than what was reported by Olatunde et al. [28] for his formulations. The WAC also seems to be higher in F2 than F1 one even though F1 has a higher protein content than F2. This is contrary to the report by Yusuf et al. [30] that protein functions in binding water, thus higher levels of legume protein increase the ability of complementary food to absorb water.

Reconstitution index is a measurement of how well food dissolves in water. Both samples reconstituted easily in water with appropriate thickness and consistency. The values for reconstitution index of F1 and F2 are slightly lower than those reported by Yusuf et al. [17]. The pH level has been reported to affect solubility of food products and formulation, firmness and characteristics of protein gels [31]. However, the pH of the F2 formulation is slightly higher to that of F1. This might have been as a result of further roasting of some of the F1 formulation. It is important to note that the pH of both formulations is almost neutral, 6.15 and 6.20 for F1 and F2 respectively, this shows that the formulation is neither alkaline in nature nor highly acidic.

Mineral elements are sources of micronutrients essential for healthy brains, bones and bodies when consumed in adequate quantities. The inorganic or mineral constituents of the foods are mostly found in the ash and protein content, these contain adequate supply of minerals like calcium, phosphorus and iron, which are essential for the formation of bones, teeth and blood components [22]. From the data obtained, significant differences were observed in the amounts of iron, potassium and magnesium of F1 and F2. The values reported for all samples are higher than those reported by Omueti et al. [31]. The F1 formulation recorded the highest levels of sodium, iron, potassium and copper while F2 seemed to have higher amounts of calcium, phosphorus and magnesium which are similar to what Menure et al. [32] reported. He also observed and reported an increase in iron and calcium levels with roasted food.

No significant difference was observed between both samples in the first and second week. Low concentrations of free fatty acids and peroxide values recorded indicate low level of rancidity which is used to evaluate the level of food palatability over time. The lack of significant difference in these values over time maybe attributed to short storage period, good storage conditions and low concentration of oily seeds in the formulation. This is in agreement with the work of Solomon 2005 [33] that peroxide formulation during storage of cereal and legume based complementary food is slow at first during an induction period which varies from a few weeks to several months depending on the particular oil/fat, air, and room temperature. This means that the formulation can be kept for weeks without spoilage contrary to other locally made complementary foods. Solomon 2005 [33] also reported that rancidity was accompanied by FFA formation and is often used as a general indication of the condition and edibility of oil-containing products; flours containing more than 15% FFA are considered unsuitable for use. The low level of moisture recorded for the sample also helps increase the shelf life of these foods as moisture is also one of the parameters for determining storage stability.

A significant difference was noted in the levels of anti-nutritional properties (oxalate and phytate) of F1 and F2. It was recorded that F2 has the lowest levels of antioxidants which are lower than the values reported by Yusuf et al. [17] except for F1 phytate content which appears to be in a similar range with values he reported. The low values of the antinutrients in these samples are probably due to heat treatment which has been reported to lower level of antinutrients by Mohammad et al. [19]. Lower levels of these antinutrients signify an increase in the bioavailability of mineral elements in foods. When present in food, oxalate becomes oxalic acid which has the ability to bind to mineral elements such as calcium and sodium making them hard to digest and unobservable. Phytate on the other hand limits the bioavailability of nutrients of nutrients in the gastrointestinal tract.

Values recorded for organoleptic properties are similar to what was reported by Muhimbula et al. [34], he noted that roasting of cereals and legumes greatly enhances aroma, texture and flavor of food. A similar observation was made by menure et al. [32] who reported a higher score of overall

acceptability for roasted samples. This is probably due to the release of maillard flavor and caramelization reaction that happens during roasting Menure et al. [32]. Akinsola et al. [20] also recorded similar findings in terms of color, with the most preferred being the sprouted sample which takes on the same color as soaked sample after processing.

The variations observed in amino acid content reflect the differential impact of processing methods on amino acid stability and retention. Soaking is known to reduce the loss of thermolabile nutrients, whereas roasting can lead to significant losses due to exposure to high temperatures [35]. The essential amino acid index (EAAI) categorizes protein quality. Using the benchmark [36], both formulations fall within the range of useful to good quality, indicating the formulations provide essential amino acids needed for optimal growth and development in children. The higher amino acid content in F1 compared to F2 highlights the nutritional advantage of soaking over roasting, especially in preserving thermolabile amino acids like tryptophan and leucine.

The results align with previous studies. For phenylalanine and leucine, Adebowale et al. [37] reported a decrease in these amino acids during high-temperature processing methods like roasting, likely due to thermal degradation. The lower levels of tryptophan and methionine in F2 compared to F1 are consistent with findings by Onimawo et al. [38], which demonstrated the susceptibility of sulfur-containing amino acids to heat damage. The minimal variation in arginine content mirrors findings by Uchechukwu-Agua et al. [39], who observed that arginine is relatively heat-stable during roasting. The unexpected increase in threonine in F2 agrees with Ezeocha et al. [40], who noted that some amino acids might become more bioavailable after heat treatment due to protein unfolding. This study highlights that processing methods significantly influence the nutritional quality of complementary foods. Soaking preserves most amino acids better than roasting, making it a preferred method for enhancing protein quality in complementary food formulations. However, roasting could still be advantageous for improving threonine bioavailability. These findings underscore the importance of selecting appropriate processing techniques to meet nutritional requirements in complementary feeding programs.

Soaking appears to be more effective in preserving β -carotene content compared to roasting. The higher β -carotene level in F1 can be attributed to the milder conditions of soaking, which likely minimize oxidative and thermal degradation of β -carotene. In contrast, roasting involves exposure to higher temperatures, which can result in the breakdown of heat-sensitive compounds like β -carotene [35].

The significant reduction of β -carotene in F2 is consistent with findings from Adebawale et al. [44] who reported that high-temperature treatments lead to a decline in carotenoid content due to thermal degradation and oxidation. Similarly, Ezeocha et al. [40] noted that roasting reduces the β -carotene content of cereal-legume-based foods, particularly when exposure to high temperatures is prolonged. The retention of β -carotene in complementary foods is crucial, as it serves as a precursor to vitamin A, an essential nutrient for vision, immune function, and growth in children. The higher β -carotene content in F1 suggests that soaking is a more suitable processing method for ensuring adequate provitamin A levels in complementary food formulations. This underscores the importance of selecting processing methods that balance nutritional retention with sensory and functional attributes.

The higher iodine value in F1 suggests that soaking is more effective in preserving iodine content compared to roasting. Iodine is a volatile and heat-sensitive nutrient and the exposure to high temperatures during roasting likely leads to significant losses through volatilization and degradation Obatolu et al. [35]. Conversely, the mild conditions of soaking help to minimize nutrient loss which preserves the iodine content in the formulation.

The reduction in iodine value observed in F2 aligns with findings from Adebawale et al. [37], who reported that high-temperature processing methods, such as roasting, lead to substantial losses of volatile nutrients, including iodine. Similarly, Ezeocha et al. [40] noted that traditional processing methods involving heat can significantly reduce iodine levels in fortified or naturally rich foods. Iodine is an essential micronutrient that plays a critical role in thyroid function and cognitive development, especially in children. The results emphasize the importance of selecting processing methods like soaking, which better preserve iodine,

to enhance the nutritional value of complementary foods. This is particularly important in regions where iodine deficiency remains a public health concern.

The microbial analysis of the complementary food formulations was conducted to assess their safety and wholesomeness. The counts obtained are within acceptable safety limits, confirming that the samples are microbiologically safe for consumption. The difference in microbial load between the two formulations may be attributed to the processing methods, as roasting (used in F2) generally reduces microbial load more effectively than soaking (F1) due to the higher temperatures involved Obatolu et al. [35].

The Gram-positive bacteria identified in F1 were *Corynebacterium ulcerans* and *Corynebacterium equi*, while F2 contained *Corynebacterium ovis* and *Corynebacterium ulcerans*. These bacteria are typically environmental contaminants and are unlikely to pose a risk if the samples are stored and handled appropriately. The Gram-negative bacteria isolated were *Klebsiella ozanae* (F1) and *Klebsiella edwardii* (F2). *Klebsiella* species are known to thrive in moist environments, which could explain their presence, particularly in F1, as soaking promotes a conducive environment for microbial growth Ezeocha et al. [40].

The mycoflora detected in F1 included *Aspergillus niger*, while F2 contained *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Trichoderma spp.* No detection of *Aspergillus phoenicis* or *Neosartorya fischeri* was observed in either formulation. The presence of *Aspergillus* species is not uncommon in cereal-based foods due to their natural occurrence in grains. However, their levels in this study appear to be within safe limits, as no mycotoxin-producing strains were detected. Roasting in F2 may have contributed to the elimination of *Aspergillus niger*, which was detected in F1, but this method did not completely eliminate fungal contamination, as shown by the presence of *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Trichoderma spp.* in F2. These findings align with Obatolu et al. [35], who reported that heat processing methods are effective but not absolute in eradicating fungal contaminants.

Overall, the microbial counts and types identified confirm that both formulations meet safety standards, with the potential risk of microbial

contamination minimized by proper processing and storage practices. Roasting appears to be more effective in reducing bacterial counts but is less effective in eliminating fungal contaminants compared to soaking. These results emphasize the need for hygienic handling and adequate storage to prevent microbial growth post-processing.

5.0 Conclusion

The study conducted reveals that the different processing methods have marked effects on the overall nutritional, sensory and functional profile of complementary food formulations. Due to the importance of having optimally nutritional complementary food, it is important to take into consideration every nuanced factor that can directly or indirectly help optimise the practice of formulating complementary foods for infants and young children. The results also show that the processed formulated complementary foods are nutrient-dense with acceptable sensory qualities. The soaked complementary food sample (F1) showed better performance in terms of protein, fibre, fat, Amino Acid content and energy density while the roasted complementary food sample (F2) showed better performance in terms of ash, carbohydrate, low microbial count and low level of anti-nutritional contents.

Therefore, the results of the current study provide a basis for the development of acceptable complementary foods with improved nutritional, sensory, functional properties and storage stability. Each processing method (soaking and roasting) had a varying effect on the complementary food formulation, and this can be used to target and improve specific desirable properties when preparing complementary foods.

6.0 Recommendations

- Further studies maybe needed to determine the effects of other processing methods such as fermentation, malting, germination and steaming on the nutritional profile of the formulation.
- Animal studies can be carried out to evaluate the effects of the processed formulations on the anthropometric, biochemical and haematological parameters on the animal subjects.

- There is a need for government to sensitize and create awareness among mothers on the effects of these processing methods on complimentary food.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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